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The Satisfaction with Family Relationships in the Italian Regions during the Period 2005-2021

It decreased by 5.12% on average in the Italian regions

Istat calculates satisfaction with family relationships in the Italian regions between 2005 and 2021. Satisfaction with family relationships is defined as the percentage of people aged 14 and over who are very satisfied with family relationships out of the total number of people in 14 years and older.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of family relationships in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of satisfaction with family relationships with an amount equal to 42.9 units, followed by Umbria with an amount of 40.4 units, and from Lombardy with an amount of 38.4 units. In the middle of the table are Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 35.1 units, followed by Tuscany with an amount of 33.8 units, and Marche with a value of 31.6 units. Puglia closes the ranking with an amount of 24.6 units, followed by Campania with an amount of 23.2 units and Basilicata with a value of 23.00 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in family relationships between 2005 and 2021. Umbria is in first place by value of the percentage change in family relationships between 2005 and 2021 with a corresponding value of 11.91%. to a variation from an amount of 36.10 units up to 40.40. Valle d'Aosta follows with a percentage variation equal to 7.34% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 32.70 in 2005 up to a value of 35.10 units in 2022. Veneto is in third place with a variation equal to an amount of 5.29% equal to an amount from 35.90 units in 2005 up to 37.80 units in 2022. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a variation equal to -3.66% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 32.80 units in 2005 up to a value of 31.60 units in 2022. Lazio follows with a variation equal to -4.11% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 29.20 units up to a value of 28.00 units between 2005 and 2022. Abruzzo closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -15.75% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 36.20 units up to a value of 30, 50 units between 2005 and 2022. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a variation equal to a variation of -17.42% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 44.20 units in 2005 to 36.50 units in 2022 Emilia Romagna is in last place with a variation equal to -18.20% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 43.40 units in 2005 up to a value of 35.50 units in 2022. Overall the value of satisfaction with family relationships decreased in the Italian regions on average from an amount of 34.15 units in 2005 to a value of 32.40 units in 2022, or a reduction of -1.75 units equivalent to -5.12%.

Satisfaction with family relationships in the Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. Satisfaction with family relationships decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. Specifically, this reduction was much more significant in regions of the Centre, the Islands and the North. In particular, satisfaction with family relationships decreased in the South with a value equal to -2.73%, in the North-West by an amount equal to -3.33%, in the South by an amount equal to -

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4.33 %, in the North for an amount of -5.54%, in Central Italy for an amount of -5.74%, in the Islands for an amount of -6.54%, in the North-East for an amount of -8, 60%. However, even if the value of satisfaction with family relationships has decreased in Central-Northern Italy much more than in the South, the value of satisfaction with family relationships still remains higher in Central-Northern Italy than in the South. In fact, the value of satisfaction with family relationships in the South is equal to -29.7% of the corresponding value in the North-West, equal to -29.3% of the value in the North, equal to -28.8% of the value in the North -East, equal to -15.1% the value of the Centre, equal to -11.7% the value of the Islands.

Clusterization with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below, a clustering is carried out with a k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Calabria, Basilicata, Puglia, Sicily, Molise, Campania, Lazio, Sardinia, Abruzzo, Marche;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Veneto, Tuscany, Piedmont, Trentino Alto Adige, Liguria, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta.

We can see that considering the average of the clusters the value of C2 is higher than the value of C1, i.e. $C2 > C1$. The clustering shows a clear contrast between the Central-Northern regions which have medium-high levels of satisfaction with family relationships and the Southern regions which have low levels of satisfaction with family relationships. The data turns out to be counterfactual. In fact, the population of Southern Italy is generally considered to be more traditional and tied to family relationships. The metric analysis instead highlights the greater capacity of the Northern regions to be efficient also from the point of view of family relationships. The Marche is the only region in Central Italy to participate in Cluster 1, i.e. the cluster that has the lowest levels of satisfaction with family relationships.

Conclusions. Satisfaction with family relationships decreased between 2005 and 2021 by approximately 5.12% on average for the Italian regions. Between 2005 and 2011, satisfaction with family relationships grew from an amount of 34.14% to a value of 36.51%. Subsequently, the value of satisfaction with family relationships decreased until reaching an absolute minimum in 2021 with an amount of 31.92 and then rising to 32.39% in 2022. The clustering and macro-regional analysis shows a generalized reduction in the value of satisfaction with family relationships. The regions of Central-Northern Italy appear to have much higher levels of satisfaction with family relationships than the corresponding values in the southern regions. A paradoxical condition arises from this: the regions of Southern Italy, generally considered more linked to family traditions, record much lower levels of satisfaction with family relationships than the regions of Central-Northern Italy. In general, the value of satisfaction with family relationships tends to decrease in all Italian macro-regions. A pillar of Italian culture is thus called into question. In fact, Italians, generally known abroad for their attachment to the family, demonstrate a condition of dissatisfaction and deterioration of family relationships which portends a total change in the value and behavioural structure of Italian society.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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References

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Risk of Poverty in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207368>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rate of Fatal Accidents and Permanent Disability in the Italian Regions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072954>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Overeducated Employed in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022. In Il Sud Est. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072464>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rate of Non-Participation in Work in the Italian Regions During the Period 2018-2022. In Il Sud Est. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10051891>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Inadequate Literacy Skills in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10004952>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Transformation of Workers from Unstable to Stable in the Italian Regions. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10064573>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Severe Housing Deprivation in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208073>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Net Income Inequality in the Italian Regions between 2004-2020. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139675>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Involuntary Part Time in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139773>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Employed People Who Work from Home in the Italian Regions. In Il Sud Est. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139635>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Reading of Books and Newspapers in the Italian Regions Between 2005 and 2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10030226>

Leogrande, A. (2023). STEM Graduates in the Italian Regions in the Period 2012-2020. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10011469>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Perception of Employment Insecurity in Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116216>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Inadequate Numerical Skills in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10005147>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Severe Material Deprivation in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207725>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Gross Disposable Income Per Capita in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2021. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139733>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Great Difficulty of Making It to the End of the Month in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251530>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Overburden of the Cost of Housing in the Italian Regions during the Period 2004-2021. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251941>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Non-Regular Employment in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2020. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076862>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Employees with Low Pay in the Italian Regions in the Period 2008-2020. In Il Sud Est. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071325>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Employment Rate in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10030613>

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Use of Libraries in the Italian Regions in the Period 2019-2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10030388>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Employed in Temporary Jobs for at Least 5 Years in the Period 2018-2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10065028>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Inadequate Literacy Skills in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10004956>

Leogrande, A. (2023). Satisfaction with the Working Condition in the Italian Regions between 2018 and 2022. In International Web Post. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114258>

Appendix

Andamento della soddisfazione per le relazioni familiari. Media delle regioni italiane. Fonte: ISTAT-BES.

Macro-Regioni	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	32,7	29,9	26,8	24,3	29	29,4	35,8
Nord-ovest	32,4	30,4	27,3	24,1	29,5	29,3	35,2
Nord-est	33,1	29,1	26,1	24,7	28,1	29,6	36,7
Centro	33,5	30,3	28,6	27,4	30,8	32,4	34,7
Mezzogiorno	38,6	36,7	31,1	26,8	28	31,1	34,3
Sud	36,5	33,8	28,9	25,3	27,5	30,3	32,1
Isole	42,9	42,3	35,4	29,8	29	32,7	38,6

Regione	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	36	38,1	38,8	43,9	39,4	39,1	38,5	44,8	35,4	36,8	35,3	35,2	36,2	37,3	37,1	34,5	33	36,5
Valle d'Aosta	32,7	33,2	35,8	40,1	31,7	33	37	40,2	31,2	34,3	40,2	36,1	35,3	32,7	34	36,5	32,6	35,1
Liguria	35,1	37,7	36,4	38,3	38,1	38,3	36	38,4	35,1	34,4	39,1	36,2	39,5	40,2	38,8	38,9	37,7	36,5
Lombardia	41,2	38,1	41,8	42,1	40,6	40,5	39,1	45,2	39	38	43,2	39,3	35,3	38,2	37,1	37,5	35,2	38,4
Trentino-Alto Adige	47,7	44,3	43,4	48,3	46	45,8	45,7	45,7	46,6	46,4	46,4	46,8	46,4	44	41,2	43,5	41	42,9
Veneto	35,9	39	36,8	39,9	37,8	38,5	39,5	43,6	40	36,8	39,1	39,8	38,5	37,5	36,5	38,8	34,3	37,8
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	44,2	40,3	43,9	43,5	42,9	45	42	40,2	39,8	38,8	41,4	39,3	37,3	38,2	35,1	39,4	38,9	36,5
Emilia-Romagna	43,4	41,8	45	45	41	41,4	40,4	40,5	37,1	43,7	39,8	36,6	38,7	39,2	37,1	36,8	35,7	35,5
Toscana	38	36,6	37,8	40,3	42,2	45,4	40,3	37,2	39	37	36,5	38,5	35,6	37,3	36,6	36,9	33,8	33,8
Umbria	36,1	37	40,8	41,7	37,8	33,7	37,9	38,4	40,3	37,7	39	32,5	35,7	37,1	37,5	35,2	34,8	40,4
Marche	32,8	31,1	32,4	34,1	31,7	36,3	33,4	34,6	32,7	33,3	32	31,4	33,7	33,4	32,6	29	32,8	31,6
Lazio	29,2	31,8	29,7	30,2	33,3	30,9	30,8	30,1	28,5	33	30,7	27,7	31,1	29,7	31,2	31,3	29,6	28
Abruzzo	36,2	26,4	30,5	30	31,6	29,3	32	34,6	35,7	32,1	35,5	32,6	33,9	35,7	30,4	31,1	31,7	30,5
Molise	30,1	28	33,4	34,7	26,3	29,7	26	33,5	30,9	30,6	21,7	28,9	30,6	27,3	30,3	26,9	26,5	27,6
Campania	24	24,4	24,9	27,4	28,3	23,3	21,5	24,3	22,5	21	22,9	21,7	24,3	22,5	26,5	24,7	26	23,2
Puglia	23,4	26,6	23,3	24,4	25,4	28,5	29,3	27	25,8	27,3	28,1	27,6	22,2	23,8	26,1	24,4	21,5	24,6
Basilicata	25,9	26,3	30,8	26,5	32	32,2	31,7	26,2	25,7	25,6	23,5	26,8	30,5	31,2	30,5	28,1	29,3	23
Calabria	26,3	28,2	26,1	30	28,2	31,7	33,9	35,6	26,7	28,8	27,4	22,7	28	26,5	27,7	28,9	26	26,6
Sicilia	31,8	27,7	32,9	30,5	33,2	32,3	29,4	33,8	28,7	28,8	29,2	32,5	30,5	27,9	30,7	27,7	28,5	30,4
Sardegna	32,9	30,3	31,9	32,5	30,3	35,9	36,9	36,3	31,1	31,5	34,1	29,3	30,4	32,6	30	28,2	29,6	29